

Estelar

D3.1 Benchmarking of Operating System Performance

WP3: Advanced computational framework

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This project has used a standard methodology already defined by partner CIRCE and developed in the HarvRESt project (Grant Agreement number: 101136904), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the conditions of the Grant Agreement for ESTELAR project (Grant Agreement number: 101192574).

AI contribution disclosure

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT accessed May 2026, with next main purposes. I) suggest wording, ii) refine grammar, iii) standardise inputs, iv) summarize content, v) review data vi) suggest results display format. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content and take full responsibility for its accuracy and integrity.

Acronyms / Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DDR4	Double Data Rate 4
eMMC	embedded Multi-Media Card
FileIO	File Input/Output
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Gigabyte
GiB	Gibibyte
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
I/O	Input/Output
IOPS	Input/Output Operations Per Second
IRQ	Interrupt Request
KiB	Kibibyte
KVM	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
MiB	Mebibyte
MPSoC	Multiprocessor System-on-Chip
OS	Operating System
PACKET_MMAP	Memory-mapped packet socket interface in Linux
PREEMPT_RT	Preemptible Real-Time Linux
QSPI	Quad Serial Peripheral Interface
RAM	Random Access Memory
RT	Real-Time
SOM	System-on-Module

SV	Sampled Values
TLB	Translation Lookaside Buffer
ToC	Table of Contents
TPACKET_V3	Third version of the PACKET_MMAP packet capture interface
VS	Virtual Substation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D3.1 – Benchmarking of operating system performance” of the ESTELAR project. It is the result of the task “T3.1 – Assessment and benchmarking of edge local resources and operating system performance”.

The deliverable presents the assessment and benchmarking activities carried out to evaluate the performance of different operating-system configurations for local edge computational resources supporting the Virtual Substation (VS) environment. The work starts from a theoretical analysis of the considered operating-system alternatives, including configurations with virtualization capabilities, and continues with their experimental evaluation on the selected hardware platform.

The benchmarking activities focus on identifying the performance behaviour and limitations of the evaluated configurations under representative workloads, with particular attention to processing, I/O, virtualization overhead and high-rate Ethernet traffic. The results provide useful input for selecting the most suitable operating-system approach depending on the target workload and deployment scenario.

Considering that the dissemination level of this deliverable is “Public”, the dataset including the performed tests and obtained results has been made available through the ESTELAR community in [Zenodo](#).

1 Introduction

Deliverable 3.1 acts as a documented procedure for the full benchmarking process of the selected hardware and Operating Systems (OS) to be used in subsequent tasks. It describes the chosen different scenarios and benchmarking tools and defines the followed methodology to achieve the results presented throughout the document.

1.1 Context and objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to evaluate and compare the behaviour of different operating environments running on the hardware platform selected. The benchmark focuses on both general system performance and the ability of each operating environment to handle high-rate Ethernet traffic based on IEC 61850 Sampled Values.

As stated in the description of Task T3.1, the selected hardware platform is expected to meet a set of requirements, including an FPGA-based architecture with support for HSR/PRP, a multi-core CPU capable of running an embedded operating system, and the possibility of performing asymmetric processing tests.

Based on these requirements, the hardware initially considered for this task was a PCI Express-based expansion board with SR-IOV support and Xilinx UltraScale+1 programmable FPGA logic as its core element. This platform included key functionalities relevant to the project, such as security mechanisms including RBAC and port security, PTPv2-based synchronization, and network redundancy support through HSR/PRP.

However, due to constraints in raw material availability, a System-on-Module (SoM) based on a Xilinx UltraScale+ MPSoC device was ultimately selected. This decision was driven by the need to mitigate potential schedule risks arising from the global geopolitical situation and its impact on hardware supply chains and manufacturing lead times. Although the selected SoM exhibits minor differences compared to the originally envisaged platform, it provides a closely aligned architecture, based on the same Xilinx UltraScale+ MPSoC technology, and

¹ Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC device: Heterogeneous Multiprocessing Platform for Broad Range of Embedded Applications.
See [Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoCs](#), accessed June 2026

preserves the main hardware and networking capabilities required for the objectives of the task.

Since both the initially foreseen platform and the selected SoM are based on the same MPSoC device family and provide equivalent core processing and programmable logic capabilities, the results obtained with this hardware are considered representative and fully valuable for the objectives of the project.

The selected hardware device fulfils the project requirements by integrating a heterogeneous processing architecture based on a quad-core Arm Cortex-A53 processing system and FPGA programmable logic. This combination provides the flexibility required to support embedded operating systems, hardware-accelerated networking functions and asymmetric processing scenarios.

Among other capabilities, the platform supports key functions relevant to the project, including Layer 2 switching, port-based Virtual LANs (VLANs), network redundancy mechanisms, Precision Time Protocol (PTP)-based synchronization, traffic filtering mechanisms, and simplified management and monitoring through a user-friendly HTTP interface or a flexible console port.

It should be noted that the final hardware platform, whose prototyping activities are expected to be completed during the initial stages of WP5, may present some functional differences with respect to the selected SoM. Nevertheless, the final platform will preserve the key features required for the project objectives, ensuring consistency between the work performed with the selected SoM and the subsequent project developments.

Although the final equipment is intended to operate as a managed and secured Ethernet switch/router with synchronisation capabilities, this benchmark is focused on the processing platform and operating-system behaviour. Therefore, the tests are not intended to validate the complete product feature set, but to characterise the performance impact of each selected software environment under comparable conditions.

The operating environments that have been selected for the benchmark are:

- Generic Linux running directly on the hardware.
- Linux with PREEMPT_RT real-time capabilities.
- Virtualised Linux running over KVM.

The comparison aims to determine the strengths and limitations of each operating environment in terms of raw throughput, latency, jitter, scheduler behaviour, storage performance, memory access, synchronisation overhead and SV traffic handling. The benchmark also provides evidence to support architectural decisions where there may be a trade-off between maximum performance, deterministic behaviour and virtualisation flexibility.

In this context, the main objectives are:

- To establish a base Linux baseline for the selected hardware.
- To evaluate whether PREEMPT_RT improves latency, predictability or behaviour under contention.
- To quantify the overhead introduced by KVM virtualisation.
- To compare CPU, memory, FileIO, mutex and thread subsystem behaviour across the selected scenarios.
- To evaluate the ability of each operating environment to transmit and receive IEC 61850 Sampled Values traffic at increasing load levels.
- To identify the most relevant bottlenecks and configuration points for future optimisation.

1.2 Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable covers the benchmarking methodology, test setup, selected tools, expected behaviour and obtained results for the operating-system comparison performed on the target hardware platform.

The scope includes:

- Description of the hardware platform used during the benchmark.
- Description of the selected operating environments.
- Definition of the performance and resource-utilisation tests.
- Definition of the Sampled Values transmission and reception tests.
- Explanation of the selected benchmarking tools and their relevant metrics.
- Presentation and interpretation of the results obtained for each test group.
- Comparative analysis between generic Linux, PREEMPT_RT and KVM.
- Identification of performance limitations and possible follow-up optimisation actions.

The results presented in this document must be interpreted as a relative comparison between operating environments under equivalent test conditions.

Some absolute values may depend on the specific kernel configuration, storage configuration, CPU affinity, IRQ assignment, network driver configuration, virtualisation settings and benchmark parameters used during the tests.

2 Testing approach & setup

2.1 Hardware description

The hardware used in this benchmarking task is a System on Module (SoM) powered by a Xilinx UltraScale+ MPSoC device with the following characteristics:

- 4x 64bit CPU ARM-Cortex-A53
- 2x 32bit CPU ARM-Cortex-R5F
- 1x 16nm UltraScale+ FPGA

The device also incorporates up to 4GB DDR4 RAM memory, 32GB eMMC Flash memory and 512Mb QSPI Flash memory.

2.2 Selected tools for testing

2.2.1 Performance & resource utilisation testing tools

Sysbench

Sysbench² is an open-source, multi-threaded, scriptable benchmarking tool for Linux systems that tests system performance, including CPU, memory, file I/O, and database performance. It is written in C and uses LuaJIT³ for custom scripts and benchmarks, allowing users to create complex workloads to identify system strengths, weaknesses, and bottlenecks under heavy load. This tool can perform a selected benchmark by using built-in tests or custom Lua scripts, often under heavy load simulating real-world conditions, and reports detailed performance metrics, which users analyse to understand system capabilities and find bottlenecks.

The tool runs a configurable number of threads, and each one generates “requests” or “events” depending on the selected test type. The test can be terminated by time (`--time`), by total number of events (`--events`) or by the test’s own condition, depending on the module used. In sysbench version 1.x, the option `--threads` defines the number of threads, option `--events` limits the total number

² Kopytov, A. (2020). Sysbench: A modular, cross-platform and multi-threaded benchmark tool. Available at <https://github.com/akopytov/sysbench>, accessed June 2026.

³ LuaJIT: a highly optimized Just-In-Time (JIT) compiler for the Lua programming language. See <https://luajit.org/>, accessed June 2026.

of events and option `--time` limits the maximum execution time. The version used in this benchmark is sysbench 1.0.20.

As mentioned, sysbench supports several benchmark workloads. The compiled-in tests are the following:

- fileio - File I/O test
- cpu - CPU performance test
- memory - Memory functions speed test
- threads - Threads subsystem performance test
- mutex - Mutex performance test

All of the compiled-in tests have a common structure. First, the requested number of worker threads are created, and each one will run its own test loop. Each iteration of the loop is called an *event* and can have any number of operations. Sysbench keeps counters on all events across all threads. When the test finishes, statistics for all events are obtained. These resulting parameters are mostly common to all tests:

- Events per second: average number of events completed per second. This is the key performance metric for the CPU, mutex and thread tests.
- Total time: actual test duration. This is usually close to the value specified by the option `--time`, but not always exactly the same.
- Total number of events: total number of events completed during the test.
- Latency min: the Lower latency measured for an event.
- Latency avg: average latency per event
- Latency max: the highest latency observed. This is the worst-case execution.
- Latency 95th percentile: 95% of the events had a latency equal to or less than that value.
- Latency sum: The cumulative summation of the latencies of all events.
- Events (avg/stddev): Average and standard deviation of completed events per thread.
- Execution time (avg/stddev): Average and standard deviation of execution time per thread.

As a general-purpose benchmarking tool for Linux and other operating systems, Sysbench does not test kernel-specific functions. Therefore, as it is a lightweight

command-line tool that is not inherently linked to standard Linux kernel programming, it can be used on PREEMPT_RT kernels without modification and without any issues.

Using the CPU workload

When running with the CPU workload, sysbench calculates prime numbers up to a limit defined by the option `--cpu-max-prime`. This will put some stress on the CPU, but only on a very limited set of the CPUs features. The aim is to generate pure CPU load, with minimal reliance on the disk or network.

The benchmark can be configured with the number of simultaneous threads and the maximum number of prime numbers to verify.

On multithreaded tests, the idea is that the events shall be distributed fairly among all threads, i.e. all threads should execute approximately the same number of events. This is shown under fairness, the `stddev` (standard deviation) should be small in relation to the average.

This test is very useful to measure computing capability, single-thread performance, multi-thread performance, scaling when using all 4 cores and kernel overhead or virtualisation.

The output of a run would be the following:

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Prime numbers limit: 500000

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

CPU speed:
  events per second:      2.86

General statistics:
  total time:              60.1976s
  total number of events:  172

Latency (ms):
  min:                    349.39
  avg:                    349.97
  max:                    354.90
```

```

95th percentile:          350.33
sum:                      60194.98

Threads fairness:
events (avg/stddev):      172.0000/0.00
execution time (avg/stddev): 60.1950/0.00

```

Among all the output parameters of this test, the most important ones are:

- Events per second: key metric for the test. Higher values represent better CPU performance.
- Total number of events: Total work completed in 60 seconds.
- Latency avg: Average time to complete a CPU operation.
- Latency max: Worst event observed.
- Latency 95th percentile: The typical value for high latency.
- Events (avg/stddev): In 4 threads, indicates whether all threads performed a similar amount of work.
- Execution time (avg/stddev): Indicates whether the threads had balanced execution times.

Using the memory workload

The memory test performs read, write or no operations on memory blocks. When performing the test, the benchmark application will allocate a memory buffer and then read or write from it each time for the size of a pointer (32bit or 64bit) and each execution, until the total buffer size has been read from or written to. This is then repeated until the total volume of data to be transferred is reached.

Sysbench allows you to configure the block size (`--memory-block-size`), the total volume of data to be transferred (`--memory-total-size`), the type of operation (read, write or none) and the access mode (sequential or random). The documented default values include `--memory-block-size=1K`, `--memory-total-size=100G`, `--memory-oper=write` and `--memory-access-mode=seq`.

In sysbench, size options using suffixes such as K, M and G are byte-based and are effectively interpreted using binary multiples. Therefore, 1K, 1M and 1G correspond to 1 KiB, 1 MiB and 1 GiB respectively.

Here, the output of a run would be slightly different⁴:

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Running memory speed test with the following options:
  block size: 1KiB
  total size: 102400MiB
  operation: write
  scope: global

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

Total operations: 16957212 (282592.57 per second)

16559.78 MiB transferred (275.97 MiB/sec)

General statistics:
  total time:                60.0002s
  total number of events:    16957212

Latency (ms):
  min:                       0.00
  avg:                       0.00
  max:                       4.18
  95th percentile:          0.00
  sum:                       52186.41

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):       16957212.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 52.1864/0.00
```

Among all the output parameters of this test, the most important ones are:

- Transferred MiB/sec: Key metric for memory bandwidth.
- Total operations: total number of memory operations performed.
- operations per second: rate of memory operations.
- total time: actual duration of the test or time to complete a fixed load.
- latency avg: average time per operation.
- latency 95th percentile: typical value for high latency.

⁴ Sysbench reports sizes and transfer rates in MiB/s (Mebibytes per second). It uses the binary system (Base 2): 1 MiB = 1,024 KiB = 1,048,576 bytes

- latency max: worst observed access.

Using the *fileio* workload

The *fileio* test requires a set of test files to work on. Therefore, it creates a set of files during the prepare phase and then performs I/O operations on those files during the run phase. The `--file-num` option defines how many files are created, `--file-total-size` defines the total size of the set. It is recommended to set a size larger than the available memory in the hardware to prevent file caching from significantly biasing the workload behaviour.

On the run phase, `--file-block-size` defines the block size used in the operations, and `--file-test-mode` defines the access pattern. Sysbench supports sequential read (*seqrd*) or write (*seqwr*) modes, random read (*rndrd*) or writes (*rndwr*) modes, or a combination (*seqrwr* or *rndrw*). The duration of the test is specified through the `--max-time` option (in seconds).

The option `--file-extra-flags=direct` adds the “direct” flag when opening files, which attempts to reduce the effect of the kernel page cache.

The output of a run would be the following:

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Extra file open flags: directio
10 files, 180MiB each
1.7578GiB total file size
Block size 16KiB
Number of IO requests: 0
Read/Write ratio for combined random IO test: 1.50
Periodic FSYNC enabled, calling fsync() each 100 requests.
Calling fsync() at the end of test, Enabled.
Using synchronous I/O mode
Doing random r/w test
Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!
```

```

File operations:
  reads/s:          1271.89
  writes/s:         847.92
  fsyncs/s:         212.14

Throughput:
  read, MiB/s:      19.87
  written, MiB/s:   13.25

General statistics:
  total time:        60.0020s
  total number of events: 139923

Latency (ms):
  min:               0.07
  avg:               0.43
  max:               44.42
  95th percentile: 0.62
  sum:               59788.39

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev): 139923.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 59.7884/0.00

```

The key parameters of this test are:

- Reads/s: read operations per second.
- Writes/s: write operations per second.
- Fsyncs/s: disk synchronisations per second.
- read MiB/s: read throughput.
- written MiB/s: write throughput.
- latency avg: average I/O operation latency.
- latency 95th percentile: typical value for high I/O latency.
- latency max: worst observed I/O operation.

Using the mutex workload

The mutex test measures the performance associated with mutual exclusion operations. It generates load by applying multiple locks to an array of mutexes and using work loops outside the critical section.

When running the test, the Sysbench application will run a single request per thread. This request will first put some stress on the CPU by using a simple incremental loop, defined by the option `--mutex-loops` parameter. After that, it takes a random mutex (lock), increments a global variable and releases the lock again. This process is repeated several times identified by the number of locks

defined by the option `--mutex-locks`. The random mutex is taken from a pool sized by the `--mutex-num` option value.

The default values are `--mutex-num=4096`, `--mutex-locks=50000` and `--mutex-loops=10000`.

The test does not measure pure CPU performance. Rather, it measures the cost of locking/unlocking mutexes, contention between threads, scheduler overhead, the cost of context switches, the fairness between threads, and the behaviour under oversubscription.

The output of a run would be the following:

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

General statistics:
  total time:                1.2855s
  total number of events:    1

Latency (ms):
  min:                       1285.15
  avg:                       1285.15
  max:                       1285.15
  95th percentile:         1280.93
  sum:                       1285.15

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):       1.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 1.2851/0.00
```

The key parameters for this test are:

- events per second: overall test performance.
- total time: very important, as in this case the test is influenced by its internal load.
- latency avg: average synchronisation cost.
- latency 95th percentile: typical value for high latency.
- max latency: worst-case scenario observed.

- avg events/stddev: distribution of events across threads.
- avg execution time/stddev: balance of execution time across threads.

Using the *threads* workload

The threads test evaluates the operating system's thread subsystem. Each event involves synchronisation operations and voluntary CPU yields.

With thread-based processing, each worker thread is assigned a mutual exclusion, also called mutex. Mutual exclusion ensures that only one process or thread can access a shared resource or critical section at a time, preventing conflicts and data corruption. During each execution, it will loop a specified number of times, documented as the number of "yields", during which it will acquire the lock (mutex) and will perform a 'yield'. This means that it will ask the scheduler to interrupt its execution and place it back at the end of the execution queue. Then, when it is rescheduled for execution, the mutex will be released.

The specific options for this test are `--thread-yields`, which defines the number of yields per request, and `--thread-locks`, which defines the number of locks per thread. Their default values are `--thread-yields=1000` and `--thread-locks=8`.

By adjusting those parameters, it is possible to simulate scenarios with a high level of thread concurrency on the same lock, or with a high level of thread concurrency on several different locks. When lock parameter is limited to 1, for example, all threads compete for the same lock, resulting in a situation of high contention. This variant is particularly useful for comparing KVM and PREEMPT_RT, as it forces the scheduler to work harder and increases the need for synchronisation.

This test is particularly useful for comparing the kernel scheduler, the cost of context switching, yields between threads, lock contention, fairness between threads, virtualisation overhead and the predictability of the RT kernel.

The output of a run would be the following:

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)
```

```
Running the test with following options:
```

```
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time
```

```
Initializing worker threads...
```

```
Threads started!
```

```
General statistics:
  total time:                60.0026s
  total number of events:    24514
```

```
Latency (ms):
  min:                       2.38
  avg:                       2.45
  max:                       6.58
  95th percentile:          2.52
  sum:                       59961.75
```

```
Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):       24514.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 59.9618/0.00
```

The more representative parameters for this test are:

- events per second: performance of the thread subsystem.
- total number of events: work completed in 60 seconds.
- latency avg: average scheduling/synchronisation cost.
- latency 95th percentile: typical value for high latency.
- latency max: worst-case scenario observed.
- events avg/stddev: distribution of events across threads.
- execution time avg/stddev: fairness in execution time.

2.2.2 Data transmission performance testing tools

The data transmission benchmark has been focused only on the testing of the capability of the hardware on sending and processing Sampled Values frames with the different OSs selected.

For that purpose, data transmission relies on devices capable of sending great number of sampled values in accordance with the IEC 61850-9-2. The standard defines the transmission of sampled measurements in multicast Ethernet frames with a specific 8-channel measurement transmission format, 4 currents and 4 voltages with two sampling options:

- 80 samples per cycle (digital protection measurement).
- 256 samples per cycle (digital power quality measurement).

For protection at nominal frequencies of 50 and 60 Hz, the 80 samples/cycle profile yields two corresponding frame rates:

- 50 Hz: 80 samples/cycle: 4000 frames per second (one Ethernet frame every 250 μ s)
- 60 Hz: 80 samples/cycle: 4800 frames per second (one Ethernet frame every 208.3 μ s)

Therefore, the utilization of devices capable of sending and processing 4,000 frames per second was imperative for the benchmark.

In this case, for the Sampled Values reception testing, SOC-E relied on one of its own electronic equipment commercially named as RELY-TEST⁵. It is a device already used for electrical substation testing, capable of fulfilling the scope of sending 4,000 frames per second. Moreover, this device can send up to 24 parallel Sampled Values flow whilst maintaining 4000 frames per second for each flow, resulting in a total throughput capacity of 96,000 frames per second. This scenario is interesting to test the limits of each Operating System.

During the benchmark, for the packet captures in the testing platform an application which makes use of TPACKET_V3 is utilized. TPACKET_V3 is a version of the Linux kernel's PACKET_MMAP feature, designed to optimize high-speed packet capture and transmission. It provides a memory-mapped ring buffer for efficient packet processing, reducing system calls and improving performance for applications like packet sniffers or network monitoring tools. It is an ideal tool for high-speed environments like this benchmark.

On the other hand, for the Sampled Values sending test, SOC-E relied on a third-party testing device for laboratory environments, called Novus ONE PLUS from Keysight⁶, with which SOC-E already has expertise working with it. The device is

⁵ RELY-TEST, IEC 61850 Substation Testing Tool, available at <https://soc-e.com/products/rely-test/>, accessed June 2026

⁶ Novus ONE PLUS Compact, all-in-one Ethernet testing for L2 – L7 validation. Available at <https://www.keysight.com/us/en/products/ethernet-traffic-emulation/hardware-accelerators-for-protocol-and-load-test/novus-one-plus.html>, accessed June 2026.

able to process and capture the required 96,000 frames/s for the high stress testing.

For the SV sending in the platform under benchmarking, captures from the RELY-TEST sending 1, 8 and 24 Sampled Values flows have been prepared and are utilized by the platform with the tool *tcpreplay*⁷ to test the capability of each OS to handle the same performance in those three different throughput scenarios.

2.3 Targeted Operating Systems

The targeted operating-system configurations were selected to cover representative alternatives with meaningful differences at software architecture level, while also taking into account SOC-E's experience with Linux-based systems. In order to ensure a consistent comparison, the three evaluated scenarios were built using Linux kernel version 6.6.0.

2.3.1 Base Linux

Linux is an open-source operating system kernel widely adopted in embedded, industrial and server environments. Its maturity, flexibility, broad hardware support and extensive software ecosystem make it a suitable choice for the selected hardware platform, especially in scenarios requiring multi-core processing support and compatibility with standard development and evaluation tools.

2.3.1.1 Expected Performance & resource utilisation

The generic Linux scenario is used as the reference baseline for the rest of the benchmark. Since it runs directly on the hardware without a real-time kernel configuration or a virtualisation layer, it is expected to provide strong average throughput in CPU, memory and storage workloads.

The generic kernel is expected to perform well in average-case metrics such as events per second, memory bandwidth, sequential file throughput and general system responsiveness. However, it is not specifically optimised for deterministic response time. Therefore, maximum latency and jitter may be higher than in the

⁷ "Tcpreplay - Pcap editing and replaying utilities," available at <https://tcpreplay.appneta.com/>, accessed June 2026

PREEMPT_RT scenario, especially in workloads involving scheduling, synchronisation, context switching or I/O blocking.

In CPU-bound workloads, generic Linux is expected to scale well up to the number of available CPU cores. On this platform, the 4-thread CPU test is the most representative full-load case because it matches the four available Cortex-A53 CPU cores.

2.3.1.2 Expected Data transmission performance

For Sampled Values transmission and reception, generic Linux is expected to provide good average throughput due to its efficient network stack and low additional kernel overhead. It should handle low and medium SV traffic rates without packet loss if the network path, socket buffers, CPU affinity and application scheduling are correctly configured.

At maximum traffic rate, corresponding to the 24-SV scenario, the main risk is not average throughput but sustained packet handling. Packet drops may occur if the application is not scheduled quickly enough, if packet buffers overflow, or if IRQ handling and user-space processing compete for CPU time. Therefore, Linux is expected to behave well in average terms, but it may be less predictable than PREEMPT_RT under peak load or scheduling pressure.

2.3.2 Virtualised Linux over KVM

KVM⁸ (Kernel-based Virtual Machine) is a virtualisation technology built into the Linux kernel that allows multiple virtual machines with Linux, Windows or any other operating systems to be run. Each VM operates as an independent process, making efficient use of the host's resources.

In this sense, KVM turns Linux into a hypervisor, facilitating the creation, management and scalability of virtual environments.

It is widely used in servers and data centres due to its performance, security and low impact on the physical system. This makes KVM an interesting candidate for the benchmarking.

For this benchmark, qemu 8.2.2 (Debian 1:8.2.2+ds-0ubuntu1.17) and libvirt 10.0.0 have been utilized.

⁸ Kernel Virtual Machine, available at https://linux-kvm.org/page/Main_Page, accessed June 2026.

2.3.2.1 Expected Performance & resource utilisation

KVM is expected to introduce additional overhead compared with base Linux and PREEMPT_RT. CPU-bound workloads may remain relatively close to native performance when hardware virtualisation is properly configured, especially if most execution time is spent in user space.

However, workloads involving storage, timers, context switches, interrupts, synchronisation or packet processing are expected to show a clearer penalty. In these cases, execution depends on the guest scheduler, the host scheduler and the virtualisation layer.

Therefore, the expected behaviour is:

- CPU throughput close to base Linux in simple CPU tests, but with possible overhead.
- Higher latency and variability in mutex and threading workloads.
- Higher overhead in FileIO workloads, especially writes and synchronisation.
- Greater risk of packet drops or unstable throughput in high-rate SV traffic.

2.3.2.2 Expected Data transmission performance

For Sampled Values transmission and reception, KVM is expected to be the most challenging scenario. Packet processing depends on the virtual NIC, host network stack, interrupt delivery, guest scheduling and host scheduling.

As a result, low and medium SV rates may still be handled correctly. However, at maximum frame rate, especially in the 24-SV scenario, a higher risk of packet drops, reduced throughput or timing instability is expected.

2.3.3 Linux PREEMPT_RT

Real-time capabilities in the Linux kernel are increasingly recognized as a viable solution, particularly for systems built on modern silicon where precise and deterministic response times are required.

Kernel preemption is the fundamental mechanism enabling real-time behaviour in Linux. It allows the currently executing task to be interrupted so that higher-priority events can be serviced without undue delay. Without kernel preemption, deterministic response times cannot be guaranteed. The reference

implementation for real-time Linux is PREEMPT_RT, maintained under the Linux Foundation. Although it is not specifically designed to achieve the absolute lowest possible latencies, it introduces key enhancements, such as priority inheritance and the replacement of certain locking primitives, that make the Linux kernel fully preemptible and capable of predictable timing behaviour.

In this context, Real-time Ubuntu⁹, based on the out-of-tree PREEMPT_RT patch set, extends real-time functionality to the Ubuntu ecosystem. It delivers reduced kernel latencies suitable for demanding workloads and provides a time-predictable execution environment. Furthermore, Canonical offers long-term support for the Real-time Ubuntu kernel for over ten years, allowing device manufacturers to focus on product development while relying on a maintained and supported operating system foundation.

2.3.3.1 Expected Performance & resource utilisation

PREEMPT_RT is primarily intended to enhance system determinism rather than to maximize raw throughput. Some overhead may be introduced by threaded interrupt handling, more preemptible kernel paths and real-time locking mechanisms. For that reason, it would be acceptable if PREEMPT_RT showed slightly lower throughput than generic Linux in some workloads.

The expected benefit is mainly related to lower worst-case latency, lower jitter and more stable behaviour under contention. The most relevant metrics for this scenario are therefore not only events per second or MiB/s, but also maximum latency, 95th percentile latency, fairness between threads and stability between iterations.

PREEMPT_RT is expected to be especially relevant in scheduler-sensitive tests such as mutex, threading, FileIO latency and random memory access.

2.3.3.2 Expected Data transmission performance

For Sampled Values traffic, PREEMPT_RT is expected to be useful when the system is close to saturation or when different tasks compete for CPU time. If IRQ threads, capture/transmission processes and CPU affinity are properly configured, the

⁹ Real-time Ubuntu, Run the most exacting workloads for low-latency use cases with Real-time Ubuntu. Available at <https://ubuntu.com/real-time>, accessed June 2026.

real-time kernel can reduce scheduling delays and improve response-time predictability.

However, PREEMPT_RT does not automatically guarantee higher network throughput. It must be configured correctly. Its expected advantage is mainly related to stable timing, reduced latency peaks and lower probability of packet drops caused by scheduling delays.

3 Hardware benchmarking results

3.1 Performance & resource utilisation testing results

The results of this benchmarking have been separated in subchapters under the different tests performed. In each chapter, the followed methodology to reach the results is explained, the obtained results are presented and comparisons between the different scenarios and conclusions are made.

As the functionality of these tools has already been described in a previous chapter, this section focuses only on the key steps required to obtain the results.

3.1.1 CPU workload

While performing the CPU test, each single event will check prime numbers up to the provided `--cpu-max-prime`. The higher this value is, the longer it takes an event to end. Therefore, it is important to first determine an acceptable number of prime numbers to be calculated.

To do so, it is recommended to start with a single thread test, trying to find a `--cpu-max-prime` that will take at least a few seconds to complete. In this sense, a maximum prime number of 6,000,000 with 1 thread and 1 event was used. The obtained result is the following:

```
$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --events=1 --cpu-max-prime=6000000
```

```
sys-developer@3565-S-3350-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --events=1 --cpu-max-prime=6000000
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Prime numbers limit: 6000000

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

CPU speed:
  events per second:    0.09

General statistics:
  total time:           11.6606s
  total number of events: 1

Latency (ms):
  min:                  11660.40
  avg:                  11660.40
  max:                  11660.40
  95th percentile:    11732.86
  sum:                  11660.40

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):  1.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 11.6604/0.00
```

Figure 1. Sysbench CPU run of 1 event and 600000 prime numbers

Here it is determined that 6,000,000 prime numbers are enough to get roughly 10 seconds for completing one event.

With a suitable max prime number found, the next step is to run a longer test. Now the test is limited to, for example, 60 seconds, without limiting the number of events. This is important since, if the number of events is still limited to one, even though an execution time is defined, the test will be performed just until one event is performed, obtaining a similar result to the previous one. The obtained result is the following:

```
$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=6000000
```

```
sys-developer@3565-S-3350-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=600000
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Prime numbers limit: 6000000

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

CPU speed:
  events per second:    0.09

General statistics:
  total time:           69.6948s
  total number of events: 6

Latency (ms):
  min:                  11612.41
  avg:                  11615.75
  max:                  11626.65
  95th percentile:    11523.48
  sum:                  69694.48

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):  6.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 69.6945/0.00
```

Figure 2. Sysbench CPU run of 600000 prime numbers at 60 s

Checking the average latency parameter, it can be seen that it took 11,615 seconds to calculate primes up to the specified limit.

The results show a very low number of events executed and that the total time was higher than the predefined one. This means that each event takes too much time to be completed and that the test cannot complete enough events inside the predefined 60 s. This is because Sysbench waits for the thread to end its event, even though it exceeds the time.

Therefore, next the value of max prime numbers is decreased until the event period inside the defined time is maintained. In this case, after some testing with different number of prime numbers, an optimal number of 500,000 was reached to get the execution time close to 60 s.

```
$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=500000
```

```
sys-developer@3565-S-3350-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~$ sysbench cpu run --threads=1 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=500000
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 1
Initializing random number generator from current time

Prime numbers limit: 500000

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

CPU speed:
  events per second:    2.85

General statistics:
  total time:           60.0222s
  total number of events: 171

Latency (ms):
  min:                  349.59
  avg:                  350.99
  max:                  356.51
  95th percentile:    350.33
  sum:                  60019.39

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev):  171.0000/0.00
  execution time (avg/stddev): 60.0194/0.00
```

Figure 3. Sysbench CPU run of 500000 prime numbers at 60 s

It can be seen that the CPU speed has increased significantly, and so does the number of events, while the total time remains close to 60 s and the average time per event decreases significantly too. Also, it is important to note that limiting the test to a selected run time increases the repeatability between iterations and different scenarios.

To test multi-thread performance of the CPU, it is recommended to first determine the number of available threads. In this case, it is already explained that the used hardware has 4 available cores with 1 thread per core, but in Linux it can be checked with the following commands:

```
$ grep processor /proc/cpuinfo | wc -l
```

```
sys-developer@3565-S-3350-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~$ grep processor /proc/cpuinfo | wc -l
4
```

Figure 4. Linux command for checking the available CPU cores

Or

Checking the CPU info where the number of threads per CPU is shown. You can check it using the command:

```
$ lscpu
```

```
sys-developer@3565-S-3350-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~$ lscpu
Architecture:          aarch64
CPU op-mode(s):      32-bit, 64-bit
Byte Order:           Little Endian
CPU(s):               4
On-line CPU(s) list: 0-3
Vendor ID:            ARM
Model name:           Cortex-A53
Model:                4
Thread(s) per core:  1
Core(s) per cluster: 4
Socket(s):             -
Cluster(s):           1
```

Figure 5. Linux command for listing CPU characteristics of the hardware

In Sysbench, `--threads` option does not represent physical or logical CPU threads, but rather the number of execution threads (user threads) that the benchmark runs in parallel. Each of those threads executes the same calculation loop (prime number calculation in this case) and competes for the CPU time under the Linux scheduler. In this case, Sysbench does not care about the real cores of the CPU, it simply throws N threads and lets the kernel schedule them.

So, as the hardware uses 4 cores, and there is only one thread for each core available, 4 threads are first used and then the value is increased to 5-6 threads to observe an overhead.

On multithreaded tests, the aim is to obtain events to be distributed fairly among all threads, i.e. all threads should execute approximately the same number of events. This is shown under fairness, where the stddev (standard deviation) should be small in relation to the average.

```
$ sysbench cpu run --threads=4 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=500000
```



```

sys-developer@3565-S-3358-ID2-01-ESTELAR:~/cpuTest_4threads$ sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=500000
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)

Running the test with following options:
Number of threads: 6
Initializing random number generator from current time

Prime numbers limit: 500000

Initializing worker threads...

Threads started!

CPU speed:
  events per second:    9.82

General statistics:
  total time:          60.4570s
  total number of events: 594

Latency (ms):
  min:                 364.18
  avg:                 608.79
  max:                 836.85
  95th percentile:   719.92
  sum:                 361619.41

Threads fairness:
  events (avg/stddev): 99.0000/2.52
  execution time (avg/stddev): 60.2699/0.15

```

Figure 8. Sysbench CPU multithread run in an overhead scenario

```

0[|||||100.0%] Tasks: 80, 64 thr, 100 kthr; 4 running
1[|||||98.7%] Load average: 4.32 2.12 1.63
2[|||||100.0%] Uptime: 13 days, 23:40:12
3[|||||100.0%]
Mem[|||||726M/3.84G]
Swp[|||||0K/0K]

Main I/O
PID USER PRI NI VIRT RES SHR S CPU% MEM% TIME+ Command
30889063 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 66.5 0.2 0:25.23 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
30889062 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 61.4 0.2 0:27.46 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
30889066 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 61.4 0.2 0:25.29 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
30889064 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 57.0 0.2 0:25.34 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
30889065 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 49.4 0.2 0:28.94 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
30889067 sys-develo 20 0 83412 8960 7168 R 49.4 0.2 0:26.82 sysbench cpu run --threads=6 --time=60 --cpu-max-prime=50000
3076939 sys-develo 20 0 10848 4224 3072 R 1.9 0.1 0:08.74 htop

```

Figure 9. CPU usage with htop Linux tool in an overhead scenario

Comparing these results with the ones with 4 threads, it may seem that a better performance is achieved, obtaining a slight increase in CPU speed and thus a higher number of total events. But there is also an increase in the total time and average latency, which means that the threads take more time waiting for CPU.

Also, the fairness seems to have decreased, obtaining a lower cpur relationship between event average and standard deviation, but this is an expected result in this overloaded scenario, since being saturated makes it less susceptible to tiny perturbations.

As explained before, each of those threads competes for the CPU time under the Linux scheduler. Because of that, more CPU resources are used, obtaining more events, but increasing at the same time the latency between each event.

Therefore, the most representative configuration in a multithread scenario is using 4 threads, which matches the CPU topology (4C / 4T, i.e. 4 cores and 4 threads).

After this initial testing, two different CPU tests have been determined for the comparison of the different scenarios:

- 500,000 prime numbers with 1 thread and limited to 60 seconds.
- 500,000 prime numbers with 4 threads and limited to 60 seconds.

Each test has been performed for 10 iterations, and these are the obtained results when comparing the OS scenarios:

Figure 10. CPU throughput per OS

The CPU test mostly evaluates raw user-space computation and scheduler behaviour when CPU-bound threads are used. Since each event consists of prime number calculation, the workload is mainly CPU-limited and has little dependency on I/O.

In the 1-thread test, the three scenarios are very close. This indicates that neither PREEMPT_RT nor KVM introduce a significant penalty for single-thread CPU-bound execution.

The 4-thread test shows more relevant differences. PREEMPT_RT obtains the highest average throughput, around 15.3% above base Linux in this test. KVM is also

slightly above base Linux, around 3.8%, which suggests that the CPU workload is not strongly penalised by virtualisation.

Figure 11. Average, 95 percentile and maximum latency per OS on a single-thread test

Figure 12. Average, 95 percentile and maximum latency per OS on a multithread test

Latency metrics reinforce the positive behaviour of PREEMPT_RT. In the 4-thread test, PREEMPT_RT has the lowest average latency. The 95th percentile is also clearly better and maximum latency follows the same trend.

Figure 13. speedup between multithread and single-thread tests per OS

The speedup values also favour PREEMPT_RT. Base Linux reaches a 4-thread speedup of 3.38, KVM reaches 3.55 and PREEMPT_RT reaches 3.91, corresponding to efficiencies of 84.5%, 88.9% and 97.7% respectively. This indicates that PREEMPT_RT scales particularly well in this CPU workload.

CPU workload conclusion

The CPU results show that PREEMPT_RT performs better than expected. It does not introduce a measurable penalty; instead, it obtains the best throughput, the best speedup and the lowest high-percentile and maximum latencies for both the 1-thread and the 4-thread tests. KVM remains close to base Linux performance for this CPU-bound workload, confirming that this specific test is not strongly affected by virtualisation overhead.

3.1.2 Memory access performance

The memory benchmark was designed to evaluate two complementary dimensions of memory behaviour: access pattern and concurrency level.

Sequential access tests represent a favourable and predictable memory access pattern, where cache locality and hardware prefetching can be exploited efficiently. Random access tests represent a more demanding scenario, where memory accesses are less predictable and may increase cache and Translation Lookaside Buffer (TLB) pressure. TLB is a small and fast hardware cache inside the CPU that stores recent mappings from virtual to physical addresses. Each access pattern was executed using both a single and four threads, the latter matching the number of physical CPU cores available in the platform. This allows the analysis to distinguish between single-thread memory performance, multithread scalability, and the impact of irregular memory access patterns across the three tested software environments.

The different memory test scenarios that have been tested are:

- Single threaded sequential access memory test: the least demanding scenario. It usually provides a good baseline measure of single-threaded memory bandwidth. It is useful as a reference for gross performance.
- Sequential access memory test with 4 threads: main test for analysing memory bandwidth scaling with all available cores. Useful for checking whether KVM or PREEMT_RT penalize scaling.
- Single-threaded random-access memory test: represents a less favourable scenario for the memory hierarchy. As access is not linear, the processor is less able to make effective use of the cache, access prediction, prefetching and spatial locality.
- Random access memory test with 4 threads: useful to check whether the system can scale when multiple cores access memory irregularly at the same time.

These cover both the system's memory access pattern and its multithreading scalability.

A complementary fixed-load memory test was also included to evaluate the time required by each system to complete the same amount of memory work. Unlike the 60-second tests, which measure how much work can be completed within a fixed time window, this test fixes the workload size to 100G and measures the completion time and sustained throughput. This provides an intuitive comparison of the systems under a constant memory workload and helps validate whether

the relative performance observed in the time-limited tests is maintained when processing a larger fixed amount of data.

The obtained results are as follows:

Figure 14. Bandwidth comparison between sequential and random memory access per OS

Figure 15. Operational performance comparison between sequential and random memory access per OS

The memory benchmark evaluates memory throughput and memory-operation rate under sequential and random write access patterns, using both 1-thread and 4-thread configurations.

In the 1-thread sequential write case, base Linux reaches 1,121.075 MiB/s, KVM reaches 1055,320 MiB/s and PREEMPT_RT reaches 1124,445 MiB/s. Base Linux and PREEMPT_RT are almost identical, while KVM is slightly lower.

In the 4-thread sequential write case, PREEMPT_RT obtains the best result with 4,336.335 MiB/s, compared with 3,722.245 MiB/s for base Linux and 3,692.215 MiB/s for KVM. This represents approximately 16,5% more throughput than base Linux.

The random write results show a similar trend. In the 1-thread random write case, the three scenarios are again very close: 283.425 MiB/s for base Linux, 276.195 MiB/s for KVM and 284.715 MiB/s for PREEMPT_RT. In the 4-thread random write case, PREEMPT_RT reaches 1,090.205 MiB/s, compared with 944.100 MiB/s for base Linux and 968.210 MiB/s for KVM.

Figure 16. speedup comparison between sequential and random memory access per OS

The speedup results confirm this behaviour. For sequential write, PREEMPT_RT reaches a speedup of 3.83 with an efficiency of 95.7%, while base Linux reaches 3.33 and KVM reaches 3.51. For random write, PREEMPT_RT reaches a speedup of

3.86 with an efficiency of 96.4%, while base Linux reaches 3.32 and KVM reaches 3.50.

Figure 17. Memory testing latency max per OS

Maximum latency also favours PREEMPT_RT. In sequential 4-thread access, the maximum latency is 9.82 ms for PREEMPT_RT, 10.885 ms for base Linux and 21.115 ms for KVM. In random 4-thread access, PREEMPT_RT again has the lowest maximum latency at 8.785 ms, compared with 12.675 ms for base Linux and 13.105 ms for KVM.

Figure 18. Comparison between total time vs memory bandwidth per OS

The complementary fixed-load test also shows PREEMPT_RT as the best case, with the lowest total time of 351.801 s and the highest transferred rate of 291.07 MiB/s.

Base Linux follows with 353.321 s and 289.82 MiB/s, while KVM is slightly worse at 360.814 s and 283.80 MiB/s.

Memory workload conclusion

The memory results show that PREEMPT_RT is not penalised in this workload. On the contrary, it provides the best 4-thread throughput, the best scaling efficiency and the lowest maximum latency. KVM remains close in several memory throughput metrics, but it shows higher maximum latency, especially in sequential 4-thread access.

3.1.3 File I/O workload

A file I/O workload refers to the pattern and characteristics of input/output operations performed on a file system or storage device.

For this test, it is necessary to first create the test files to work on. It is recommended that the size is larger than the available memory to ensure that file caching does not influence the workload too much. However, due to storage capacity limitations, the FileIO dataset was limited to 1800Mib for this benchmark. Direct I/O was used to reduce the impact of the page cache. Therefore, the FileIO results should be interpreted primarily as a relative comparison between operating environments under identical conditions.

For generating the 10 test files, the following command was used:

```
$ sysbench fileio prepare --file-num=10 --file-total-size=1800M --file-extra-flags=direct
```

```
sysbench 1.0.20 (using system LuaJIT 2.1.0-beta3)
10 files, 184320Kb each, 1800Mb total
Creating files for the test...
Extra file open flags: directio
Creating file test_file.0
Creating file test_file.1
Creating file test_file.2
Creating file test_file.3
Creating file test_file.4
Creating file test_file.5
Creating file test_file.6
Creating file test_file.7
Creating file test_file.8
Creating file test_file.9
1887436800 bytes written in 37.55 seconds (47.94 MiB/sec).
```

Figure 19. generating required 10 test files for sysbench file I/O testing

The File I/O benchmark was designed to cover the main storage access patterns: sequential read, sequential write, random read, random write and mixed random read/write.

Sequential tests represent favourable and predictable access patterns, useful to estimate maximum read and write throughput. Random tests represent less predictable and more latency-sensitive workloads, where the operating system, filesystem, block layer and virtualization overhead may have a stronger impact. The mixed random read/write test was executed with both one and four threads, the latter matching the number of physical CPU cores available in the platform. This allows the analysis to evaluate not only raw I/O throughput, but also scalability and latency under concurrent mixed I/O load.

The different memory test scenarios that have been tested are:

- Single-threaded sequential read: the most favourable scenario for storage, as the data is read linearly. Useful as a benchmark for maximum read performance.
- Single-threaded sequential write: particularly relevant for KVM, as write performance can be significantly affected by the virtual disk configuration, the storage backend and the cache mode.
- Single-threaded random read: more demanding than sequential reading because accesses do not follow a linear pattern. This reduces the efficiency of read-ahead and can increase latency per operation.
- Single-threaded random write: one of the most demanding scenarios for the storage subsystem, because writes are not grouped in a linear way and may require more management on the part of the file system, the I/O scheduler and the device. It can clearly reveal the overhead of KVM, particularly if virtual storage introduces additional layers between the guest and the physical hardware.
- Single-threaded random read/write: a more realistic approach than measuring read-only or write-only performance, since many real-world workloads combine both operations. It is also useful for seeing how the system behaves when it must switch between read, write and synchronisation operations.

- Random read/write with 4 threads: it is clearly the most interesting File I/O test, as it is useful to see how the I/O subsystem scales when concurrency is introduced and how KVM and PREEMPT_RT affect latency and stability under concurrent mixed loads.

The obtained results are the following:

Figure 20. File I/O sequential throughput comparison

The FileIO test is more sensitive to the operating environment than the CPU and memory ones because it depends on the filesystem, block layer, storage driver, synchronisation operations and scheduling behaviour. Direct I/O was used to reduce page-cache effects, so the results are useful for relative comparison under the same conditions.

In sequential read throughput, KVM obtains the highest value with 60.695 MiB/s, compared with 51.220 MiB/s for PREEMPT_RT and 50.540 MiB/s for base Linux. This result indicates that the virtualised environment performs well in this specific sequential read case.

Sequential write shows the opposite behaviour. Base Linux reaches 45.020 MiB/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 38.475 MiB/s and KVM only reaches 9.535 MiB/s. This means KVM suffers a strong write-throughput penalty, around 78.8% lower than base Linux. PREEMPT_RT is also below base Linux in sequential write, but the reduction is much smaller, around 14.5%.

Figure 21. File I/O random operation speed comparison

Random I/O provides a clearer comparison of the storage path under less favourable access patterns. In random read, KVM is slightly ahead, followed by PREEMPT_RT and base Linux. However, random write again shows a severe KVM penalty.

Figure 22. File I/O random read/write operation scaling

For mixed random read/write, base Linux and PREEMPT_RT are almost identical in the 1-thread case: 1,935.745 total IOPS for base Linux and 1,929.645 total IOPS for PREEMPT_RT. KVM reaches 1,023.505 total IOPS, around 47% below base Linux. In the

4-thread mixed random read/write case, base Linux reaches 2,145.400 IOPS, PREEMPT_RT reaches 2,089.590 IOPS and KVM remains at 1,023.505 IOPS. This confirms that KVM does not scale in this mixed FileIO workload.

Figure 23. File I/O random read/write operation latency

Latency metrics are especially relevant. For random read/write with 4 threads, the 95th percentile latency is 2.35 ms for PREEMPT_RT, 2.48 ms for base Linux and 3.25 ms for KVM. The maximum latency is 99.61 ms for PREEMPT_RT, 181.215 ms for base Linux and 642.935 ms for KVM. Therefore, PREEMPT_RT provides the best worst-case behaviour, while KVM shows a much higher latency peak.

Figure 24. File I/O random read/write & write operations synchronization speed

The fsync results also confirm the KVM penalty. For random write, base Linux reaches 178.98 fsyncs/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 163.63 fsyncs/s and KVM reaches only 47.405 fsyncs/s. For mixed random read/write, base Linux reaches 193,645 fsyncs/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 193.060 fsyncs/s and KVM reaches 89.355 fsyncs/s.

FileIO workload conclusion

FileIO is one of the clearest differentiating benchmarks. Base Linux provides the best sequential write throughput and the best mixed random IOPS, while PREEMPT_RT remains very close in throughput and improves the worst-case latency. KVM performs well in sequential read and random read, but suffers a major penalty in write, mixed random I/O and fsync-related metrics. For workloads sensitive to storage writes or synchronisation, KVM is the weakest scenario.

3.1.4 Mutual exclusion

The mutex benchmark was selected to evaluate the cost of mutual exclusion and synchronization under increasing levels of concurrency. Tests were executed with 1, 2, 4, and 8 threads.

The 1-thread case provides a baseline without real inter-thread contention, while the 2-thread one introduces moderate concurrency. The 4-thread case matches the number of physical CPU cores available in the platform and therefore

represents the maximum natural concurrency level of the hardware. The 8-thread case intentionally oversubscribes the CPU and is used as a scheduler stress scenario, where runnable threads outnumber available physical cores.

This test set allows the analysis of synchronization overhead, latency growth, fairness between threads, and the impact of virtualization or real-time kernel behaviour under contention.

The results obtained are described below:

Figure 25. Mutex throughput for each number of threads and per OS

The mutex test evaluates synchronisation overhead, lock/unlock cost, scheduler interaction and behaviour under increasing thread count. Since this test is strongly influenced by its internal loop and lock configuration, total execution time is a key metric in addition to events per second and latency.

In the 1-thread and 2-thread cases, the three scenarios are almost equivalent. This is expected because contention is low. At 1 thread, base Linux reaches 0.785 events/s, KVM reaches 0.772 events/s and PREEMPT_RT reaches 0.787 events/s. At 2 threads, the values are 1.568, 1.546 and 1.571 events/s respectively.

The differences become clearer at 4 and 8 threads. At 4 threads, PREEMPT_RT reaches 3.040 events/s, compared with 2.620 for KVM and 2.578 for base Linux. At 8 threads, PREEMPT_RT reaches 3.046 events/s, while base Linux and KVM remain around 2.73 events/s. This indicates that PREEMPT_RT handles the mutex workload better under higher concurrency.

Figure 26. Total time required for each Mutex testing per OS

The graph of the total execution time confirms the same trend. In the 4-thread case, PREEMPT_RT completes the workload in 1.316 s, compared with 1.527 s for KVM and 1.552 s for base Linux. In the 8-thread case, PREEMPT_RT completes it in 2.626 s, compared with 2.929 s for base Linux and 2.936 s for KVM.

Figure 27. Comparison of average latency for each number of threads and per OS

Figure 28. Comparison of 95 percentile latency for each number of threads and per OS

Figure 29. Comparison of maximum latency for each number of threads and per OS

Figure 30. Comparison of maximum latency deviation per OS for 10 iterations with 4 threads

Figure 31. Comparison of 95 percentile latency deviation per OS for 10 iterations with 4 threads

Latency metrics also favour PREEMPT_RT under load. At 4 threads, the 95th percentile latency is 1,304.21 ms for PREEMPT_RT, compared with 1,533.905 ms for KVM and 1,547.590 ms for base Linux. At 8 threads, the 95th percentile latency is 2,632.28 ms for PREEMPT_RT, compared with 2,906.435 ms for base Linux and 2,932.600 ms for KVM.

Maximum latency follows the same pattern. At 8 threads, PREEMPT_RT reaches 2,623.38 ms, while base Linux reaches 2,921.605 ms and KVM reaches 2,932.65 ms. This is relevant because the 8-thread case introduces oversubscription and exposes scheduler behaviour under stress.

Mutex workload conclusion

The mutex benchmark shows one of the strongest PREEMPT_RT results. Low-contention cases are similar across all systems but, under 4-thread and 8-thread load, PREEMPT_RT provides a higher number of events/s, lower total execution time and lower high-percentile latency. KVM does not collapse in this test, but it does not provide the improvements observed with PREEMPT_RT.

3.1.5 CPU scheduler / Threading workload

The threading benchmark was selected to evaluate the behaviour of the CPU scheduler under different levels of concurrency, lock contention and CPU oversubscription.

The standard configuration uses 8 thread locks and 1000 thread yields, allowing the analysis of scheduler behaviour with low to moderate contention.

Tests with 1, 2, and 4 threads evaluate the evolution from a single-thread baseline to full utilization of the four physical CPU cores. Additional tests with a single thread lock intentionally increase contention by forcing all worker threads to compete for the same synchronisation object. Finally, the 8-thread test oversubscribes the CPU and is used as a scheduler stress scenario.

The different scenarios that have been tested are:

- Threading 1 thread with 8 locks: interesting to know what the baseline cost of the scheduler/threading workload on each system without actual concurrency is.
- Threading 2 threads with 8 locks: useful for checking how performance and latency change when there is concurrency, but not all cores are being used.
- Threading 2 threads with 1 lock: both threads are competing for the same lock. It is a moderate high-contention test, since there are only two threads, but both need to synchronise on the same resource. Useful to see how much performance degrades in each system when two threads compete for the same lock.
- Threading 4 threads with 8 locks: probably the most important standard test. Shows how each system performs when all the physical cores are utilised with a standard threading load.
- Threading 4 threads with 1 lock: the most interesting threading test for analysing severe contention, since it shows how each system performs with all cores active and maximum contention on a single lock.
- Threading 8 threads with 8 locks: an additional stress test. It does not represent the hardware's maximum rated performance, rather an oversubscription scenario with more threads ready to run than available CPUs. Interesting to see what happens when the system needs to schedule more threads than it can run simultaneously.

This test set allows the analysis of throughput, scheduling latency, worst-case behaviour, and fairness across the three software environments.

The obtained results are the following:

Figure 32. Throughput Comparison of standard thread tests with 8 locks per OS

Figure 33. Throughput comparison of standard thread tests vs high contention thread tests per OS

The threading test evaluates scheduler behaviour, voluntary yields, locks and coordination between threads. This benchmark is much more sensitive to scheduling and synchronisation than the pure CPU test.

In the standard-lock scenario, base Linux provides the highest throughput. At 1 thread, base Linux reaches 931.45 events/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 618.53 events/s and KVM reaches 405.33 events/s. At 2 threads, base Linux reaches 1,842.09 events/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 1,197.74 events/s and KVM reaches 795.88 events/s.

At 4 threads, base Linux reaches 2,558.75 events/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 2,266.87 events/s and KVM reaches 1,358.49 events/s. This is the most representative standard-lock full-load case because it matches the CPU topology. PREEMPT_RT remains relatively close to base Linux, around 11.4% lower, while KVM is around 46.9% lower.

The 8-thread case introduces oversubscription and shows a strong drop in all scenarios. Base Linux falls to 989.82 events/s, PREEMPT_RT to 589.83 events/s and KVM to 416.57 events/s. This confirms that adding more runnable threads than available CPU cores significantly increases scheduler pressure and reduces useful throughput.

The high-contention scenario, where all threads compete for one lock, is especially relevant. With 2 threads and 1 lock, base Linux reaches 674.84 events/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 277.19 events/s and KVM reaches 258.51 events/s. With 4 threads and 1 lock, base Linux reaches 394.70 events/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 300.73 events/s and KVM reaches 181.93 events/s. In this case PREEMPT_RT remains clearly above KVM, but below base Linux.

Figure 34. Comparison of 95th percentile latency of Standard threading tests

Figure 35. Comparison of maximum latency of Standard threading tests

Latency results show a more nuanced picture. In the 4-thread standard-lock case, PREEMPT_RT has the best 95th percentile latency at 1.73 ms, compared with 5.28

ms for base Linux and 6.55 ms for KVM. However, the maximum latency is 38.54 ms for PREEMPT_RT, 31.595 ms for base Linux and 60.735 ms for KVM. This means PREEMPT_RT improves the typical high-latency behaviour, while KVM shows the worst maximum latency.

In the 8-thread oversubscribed case, PREEMPT_RT does not improve latency. Its 95th percentile is 63.895 ms, similar to KVM at 63.32 ms and worse than base Linux at 25.97 ms. Its maximum latency is also the highest at 376.66 ms, compared with 249.165 ms for KVM and 149,765 ms for base Linux. This suggests that PREEMPT_RT is not automatically better under oversubscription in this specific Sysbench threading workload.

Figure 36. 95th percentile vs maximum latency for threading test with 4 threads and 1 thread lock

In the 4-thread / 1-lock high-contention case, base Linux again has the best average latency and p95. PREEMPT_RT is between base Linux and KVM for throughput, but its maximum latency is higher than base Linux and lower than KVM. KVM is consistently the weakest scenario in throughput and often in latency.

Threading workload conclusion

The threading benchmark is the clearest case where generic Linux remains the strongest option in raw scheduler throughput. PREEMPT_RT performs well in the representative 4-thread standard-lock case and provides an excellent 95th percentile latency there, but it does not improve all threading scenarios, especially under 8-thread oversubscription or severe lock contention. KVM shows a significant penalty across almost all threading configurations, confirming that this workload is highly sensitive to virtualisation overhead.

3.2 Data transmission performance testing results

Validation of external traffic equipment

As previously explained, two different devices have been utilized for this test battery, along with the hardware under benchmark, namely the RELY-TEST and the Novus ONE PLUS.

The external traffic generation and capture setup was validated before comparing the operating systems. The original captures show reference throughputs of 4,000 frames/s for 1 SV, 32,000 frames/s for 8 SVs and approximately 96,000 frames/s for 24 SVs. These values provide the baseline used to evaluate whether the platform under test can reproduce or process the required traffic level.

The following figures show the throughput captured by the Novus ONE PLUS for each of the Sampled Value flow sent by the RELY-TEST:

Link State	Frames Tx.	Valid Frames ...	Frames Tx. R...	Valid Frames Rx. Rate
Link Up	0	11.193	0	4000

Figure 37. Throughput reception of 1 SV from RELY-TEST to Novus ONE PLUS

Duplex Mode	Line Speed	Link State	Frames Tx.	Valid Frames ...	Frames Tx. R...	Valid Frames Rx. Rate
Full	1000Mbps	Link Up	0	272.152	0	32.000

Figure 38. Throughput reception of 8 SVs from RELY-TEST to Novus ONE PLUS

Duplex Mode	Line Speed	Link State	Frames Tx.	Valid Frames ...	Frames Tx. R...	Valid Frames Rx. Rate
Full	1000Mbps	Link Up	0	1.550.068	0	95.990

Figure 39. Throughput reception of 24 SVs from RELY-TEST to Novus ONE PLUS

The captures of this testing are used in the Sampled Values transmission performance testing.

3.2.1 Sampled Values transmission performance

Since the RELY-TEST requires some time to send simultaneously all the defined Sampled Values frames, the captures have been filtered to erase the first part until

the maximum throughput is reached. This way, by using *tcpreplay*, the OS shall emulate and send the maximum throughput.

The transmission benchmark evaluates the capability of each operating environment to replay SV traffic using *tcpreplay* and have it captured by the Novus ONE PLUS equipment.

The results are as follows:

Figure 40. SV sending throughput per OS

Figure 41. Throughput percentage in relation to reference traffic per OS

For the 1-SV scenario, all operating systems are close to the 4,000 frames/s reference. Base Linux reaches 3,822 frames/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 3,766 frames/s and KVM reaches 3,642 frames/s. This corresponds to 95.55%, 94.15% and 91.05% of the reference throughput respectively.

For the 8-SV scenario, none of the systems reaches the 32,000 frames/s reference. Base Linux reaches 23,143 frames/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 21,087 frames/s and KVM reaches 20,260 frames/s. This corresponds to 72.32%, 65.90% and 63.31% of the reference throughput. Base Linux is the best scenario, while PREEMPT_RT and KVM are lower.

The 24-SV scenario is the decisive stress case. The reference throughput is approximately 95,990 frames/s. Base Linux reaches 45,219 frames/s, PREEMPT_RT reaches 35,513 frames/s and KVM reaches 17,482 frames/s. This corresponds to 47.11%, 37.00% and 18.21% of the reference throughput. Therefore, none of the operating systems reaches the full 24-SV target in transmission, although base Linux performs best and KVM is clearly the weakest.

Since the Novus ONE PLUS captured essentially the same number of frames as *tcpreplay* reports as sent, the main limitation appears to be the ability of the

platform and OS to generate/replay traffic at the required rate, rather than packet loss after transmission.

SV transmission conclusion

The SV transmission test shows that the platform can handle the 1-SV case correctly, but throughput progressively falls below the reference as the number of SV streams increases. Base Linux provides the best transmission performance, PREEMPT_RT is in the second place, and KVM shows a severe degradation at maximum load. The 24-SV target of approximately 96,000 frames/s is not reached by any scenario in the measured results.

3.2.2 Sampled Values reception performance

The reception benchmark evaluates whether the platform can receive and process SV traffic generated by the RELY-TEST without losing frames.

The results are the following:

Figure 42. Percentage of lost frames per OS

In the 1-SV and 8-SV scenarios, all operating systems receive all frames with 0% loss. This is an important result because it confirms that the basic receive path and the capture application are valid for low and medium traffic rates.

The 24-SV scenario introduces packet loss in all environments. Base Linux gets the best results by only losing a 10.7% of the sent frames, while KVM has a corresponding loose frame percentage of 16.76% and PREEMPT_RT 32.04%, being this last one the worst case in this scenario.

These results show that the receive path is able to sustain 1-SV and 8-SV loads, but not the maximum 24-SV load. Base Linux provides the best reception result at maximum load, followed by KVM. PREEMPT_RT shows the highest absolute and relative loss in the 24-SV reception case.

This result is important because it differs from the expectation that PREEMPT_RT would automatically improve packet reception determinism. A likely explanation is that PREEMPT_RT requires specific tuning to provide benefits in this workload. IRQ thread priorities, CPU affinity, capture application priority, socket ring size and competing kernel threads may have a strong influence. If those parameters are not tuned correctly, PREEMPT_RT may not improve high-rate packet reception and can even perform worse than the generic kernel.

SV reception conclusion

The SV reception test confirms that all operating systems can receive 1-SV and 8-SV traffic without loss. At 24 SVs, none of the scenarios sustains the full receive load. Base Linux is the best case with 10.70% loss, KVM follows with 16.76% loss, and PREEMPT_RT is the weakest in this specific measurement with 32.04% loss. Further tuning is required before concluding that PREEMPT_RT is unsuitable for this workload, because real-time Linux performance depends strongly on IRQ, scheduler and CPU-affinity configuration.

4 Discussion

The benchmark results show that the behaviour of each operating environment depends strongly on the workload type. No single operating system dominates all metrics.

Generic base Linux Linux remains the most robust baseline for raw I/O and network throughput. It provides the best sequential write throughput, the best mixed random FileIO throughput, the best threading throughput and the best SV transmission and reception results at maximum traffic load. These results make it the strongest general-purpose scenario when maximum throughput is the primary objective.

PREEMPT_RT performs better than expected in CPU, memory and mutex workloads. It obtains the best 4-thread CPU throughput, the best CPU scaling efficiency, the best memory throughput in the 4-thread cases and the best mutex results under higher thread counts. It also significantly improves FileIO worst-case latency in the random read/write 4-thread test. These results support the idea that PREEMPT_RT can improve predictability and, in some workloads, it may also improve throughput.

However, PREEMPT_RT does not improve all scheduler-sensitive or packet-processing cases. In the threading workload, base Linux Linux remains stronger in raw throughput. PREEMPT_RT improves the 95th percentile latency in the 4-thread standard-lock case, but it performs worse under 8-thread oversubscription and does not dominate the high-contention lock scenarios. In SV reception, PREEMPT_RT shows the highest loss at 24 SVs. Therefore, PREEMPT_RT should not be considered automatically better without workload-specific tuning.

KVM behaves as expected in most cases. It remains close to base Linux in the pure CPU test and performs reasonably in some memory and read-oriented FileIO metrics. However, it suffers clear penalties in write FileIO, fsync-related metrics, threading workloads and high-rate SV traffic. This confirms that virtualisation overhead becomes much more visible when the workload depends on I/O, synchronisation, context switching or packet processing.

The Sampled Values tests are especially relevant for the target application. Transmission results show that the platform does not reach the 24-SV reference throughput in any OS scenario. Reception results show that all systems handle 1-

SV and 8-SV traffic without loss, but all lose frames at 24 SVs. This indicates that the maximum traffic case exceeds the currently measured processing capability or configuration of the platform.

5 Conclusions

The benchmark provides a comparative view of generic Linux, Linux PREEMPT_RT and virtualised Linux over KVM on the same hardware platform.

Generic Linux provides the strongest overall baseline. It performs especially well in FileIO throughput, threading throughput and Sampled Values transmission / reception. For workloads where maximum average throughput is the main objective, generic Linux is the safest reference scenario.

PREEMPT_RT provides very strong results in CPU, memory and mutex workloads. It achieves the best CPU 4-thread throughput, the best CPU scaling efficiency, the highest memory throughput in 4-thread tests and the best mutex behaviour under higher concurrency. It also reduces FileIO maximum latency in the mixed random 4-thread case. These results show that PREEMPT_RT can bring real benefits beyond determinism in some workloads.

Nevertheless, PREEMPT_RT does not automatically improve every latency-sensitive workload. Its threading results are mixed, and its 24-SV reception result is worse than base Linux and KVM in the current measurements. Before making a final decision about PREEMPT_RT for high-rate packet processing, additional tuning should be evaluated, especially IRQ affinity, IRQ thread priorities, capture-thread priority, socket ring size and CPU isolation.

KVM provides architectural flexibility, but it introduces significant overhead in several relevant workloads. The CPU benchmark shows that virtualisation overhead can be low for pure computation, but FileIO writes, fsync operations, threading and high-rate SV traffic show clear degradation. KVM is therefore less suitable for the most demanding real-time or high-throughput packet-processing scenarios unless the virtualisation path is further optimised.

For the Sampled Values benchmark, the 1-SV and 8-SV receive cases are successfully handled by all operating systems. However, the 24-SV case is not sustained without loss in reception, and the 24-SV transmission reference throughput is not reached by any scenario. This indicates that the maximum SV requirement is the key limitation found in the current benchmark. Also, it is important to note that in SV transmission, none of the considered scenarios has been able to achieve maximum reference throughput.

These results should not be interpreted as a general limitation of the hardware platform, but rather as the limit observed for the evaluated benchmark configuration. In this task, the SV processing chain has been assessed mainly under a monolithic software approach, where the reception, processing and transmission workload is concentrated in the same operating-system environment. Under this configuration, the 24-SV case represents the most demanding scenario and exposes the main performance bottleneck of the current setup. For higher SV densities, alternative implementation strategies may be required, such as distributing the workload across dedicated processing resources or offloading specific time-critical functions to additional processing elements available in the MPSoC architecture.

Overall, the final operating-system selection should consider the target workload. Base Linux is the best current candidate for maximum SV throughput and general I/O robustness. PREEMPT_RT is promising for deterministic and synchronisation-heavy workloads, but it requires additional network-specific tuning. KVM should be selected only if the benefits of virtualisation outweigh the measured performance penalties in I/O, threading and high-rate Ethernet traffic.